

BLENDLED LEARNING, CHARACTER EDUCATION IN SINGLE-PARENT FAMILY FOR ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

Adolescence is a period of self-discovery. Adolescence is sometimes identified by some people as a period of rebellion followed by various cases of juvenile delinquency. The purposes of this study were to describe the role of family education in a single parent family can play a role in shaping the character of characterized children and the application of the character education itself. This research used descriptive qualitative method with purposive sampling. The results of this study showed that making command or prohibition were not the main weapon in applying character education in family context. In fact it was the technique how the parents should guide the teenagers which is needed to be emphasized. Excessive given on the restrictions and instructions will not educate adolescents to have an adult personality in thinking and behaving, but these actions make them feel as an individual who is always restricted, confined, and they try to find freedom which results in becoming a rebel. The achieved conclusion is the parents should persuade their children to be open with what they think and feel in themselves, and thus their values and characters is likely to be easily controlled.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a period of self-discovery, a transition phase from the children to the maturity age, a phase where these adolescents want to know the result of self-discovery immediately. Most adolescents with obesity will become obese adults, thus increasing their risk of developing serious and debilitating health conditions (Nogueira, 2014: 740). In addition to social bonding variables, the questionnaire included questions measuring psychological well-being and a number of serious life events that might have an impact on the behaviour of young people (Josine, et al., 2014: 336). In the social maturity stage, adolescents' experience, on a period of puberty followed with a variety of emotional grades in them, an immaturity sometimes is recognized by some people as a period of rebellion followed with various cases of juvenile delinquency. (Kartono (2005, pp 14), a sociologist said "*Kenakalan Remaja* or in English known as juvenile delinquency is an association of compulsive occurrence in adolescence caused by a type of social ignore. As a result, they develop a form of deviant behavior". With some deviations on their behavior, it is prone to trigger a variety of juvenile delinquency resulting in their moral degradation.

In the development of the unfolding digital transformation, the textbook has gone through changes over time (Wang, & Xing, 2018: 3). The technology and electronics in the current era are developing so rapidly that it can access information without limits. Technologies can be used to support the formal education of children in mobile learning communities (Chen, 2015: 246). With the tendency to use this

unlimited internet, which can be accessed by all ages; even by children and adolescents, children should get parental supervision while using the internet. Mobile phones have found use in almost every aspect of modern day human life (Alrasheedi, et al., 2016: 253).

The lack of wisdom or judgment while using the internet for adolescents, who are having a high level of curiosity, leads to various acts of crime due to the lack of responsibility sense. Curiosity, high selfishness, and the desire of being famous among their friends become the background of children in the age of becoming teenagers to act desperately and commit a crime in order to fulfill the children's egoism. Technology development also contributes to the changes in the culture and behavior of Indonesian children. Understanding the needs and perceptions of potential users is essential to ensure sustainable use of newly introduced technology applications in developing countries (Yamaguchi and Vaggione, 2008). The proliferation of smartphones has changed the traditional way of using mobile phones (Yew Siang Poong, et al., 2017: 57).

Nowadays, many teenagers and underage children are familiar with cigarettes, drugs, free sex, brawls, theft, teenage marriages, and engaged in other illegal activities that deviate from the prevailing norms in society and deal with the law. Model integrates the reviewed theories by examining predictors and correlates of violence at various levels of the social ecology (Dardis, et al., 2015: 145). Based on the the National Narcotics Agency (*Badan Narkotika Nasional*) in collaboration with the University of Indonesia showed that the total number of drug abusers is 1.5% of the population or 3.2 million people. It consists of 69% regular user group and 31% of addicted group with the proportion of men by 79% and 21% of women with the mortality rate of narcotic addiction are 15.000 people died within 1 year.

An additional data from the National Family Planning Coordinating Board (BKKBN) in 2011 showed that 2.4 million of abortion rate with 700-800 thousand abortion practitioners were teenagers and 1283 cases of HIV / AIDS where 52,000 estimated people to be infected and 70% of them were adolescents. Assumes adolescent males' masculinity is similar to hegemonic adult masculinity and focuses on characteristics such as sexual prowess, objectification of women, and an incapacity for intimacy in romantic and sexual relationships (David L. Bell, et al., 2014: 201). Consequently, it is necessary to inculcate character education to the adolescents for their personality development in order to raise the awareness of critical thinking as a prevention of not falling into the wrong association/organization or even having an identity crisis as a result of the individual itself.

Based on the background above the problems can be formulated as follows: 1) Is family education in single parent family can play a role in shaping the adolescents' character? and 2) How is the application of the character education use blended learning? So that researchers know the tendency of personality participant 1 and participant 2 is only raised by a person who only consists of the single parent.

2. METHOD

This research used descriptive qualitative method with purposive sampling. The participant of this study were participant 1 and participant 2 the parent as children who were raised by single parent. participant 1 is a child raised by his father because of divorce, while participant 2 is taken care of by his mother because his father has died. participant 1 and participant 2 parents were used as primary data while participant 1 and participant 2 were used as secondary data. One sample parent participant 2 was obtained through a key person information.

The data were collected through interview and observation. The data in this study were collected by using several instrument tools, including interviews guides, observation sheets, and documents, and making notes from the result of interviews, observations, and documents analysis.

This research used an inductive approach with an interactive model as the data analysis. The process of qualitative analysis in this study had 4 important components, including; data collection, data reduction, data display, and data conclusion and verification.

3. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The background of heterogeneous society; poor to the upper middle-class economy background or people who go to school to those who have worked, Indonesia needs various learning styles. Blended learning model is a trend that has been developed as a learning model for schools. The media for this learning model can be in the form of internet-based learning, teleconference, video conferencing and others. A blended learning approach is being used in on-campus courses which include hard copy study materials, face-to-face sessions and communication via email, coupled with the more recent internet based message boards and other online resources (Bawaneh, 2011: 63). In general, blended learning model is an internet-based learning with an open learning environment; limitless information can be accessed through the internet that aims to facilitate the learning process and develop students' knowledge through meaningful interactions. According to their definition, blended learning is the transfer of “right” skills to the “right” person at the “right” time by matching the “right” learning technologies with the “right” learning style for the purpose of achieving the learning objectives (Yapici, & Akbayin, 2012: 229).

These backgrounds and the sophisticated technological developments degrade the parenting process in childcare. Parents who argue that they are busy with work provide gadgets for their children to prevent the fussiness. It is also a pity that these children, who have not been able to be responsible, are getting their own gadget as a monitoring device. Parenting is not always easy and doing it alone creates additional challenges (Briggs, Cox, et al., 2015: 129). Some of the single parents also provide gadget to their children for other reasons; replace the guilty feeling of not being able to give sufficient love or busy with work, and prevent their children become outdated. Unfortunately, in some distressed single-parent families, the single parent acts out the couple's way of handling conflict as a parenting strategy for their child behavior management (Briggs, Leary, et al., 2005). Teenagers who do not have responsibility for themselves are capable of doing detrimental actions which also affect their future. Consequently, underage children often access pornographic sites or applications that endanger the children.

Education given via tools such as letters, videos, cassettes and television is called “distance education” (Yapici, & Akbayin, 2012: 228). There are numerous mistakes in Indonesian society that rely on the school 100% to educate their children who are expected to have strong characters. Hence, after their children are sent to school, the parents think their responsibilities have been completed. After all, personality education that instructed only from the school is not sufficient. The understanding of character education also needs to be taught in the family and community environment. As stated by Sarwono (1998, pp 29), said that the family is the primary environment in each individual. Before the child gets to know the wider environment, he first recognizes his family environment. Therefore, before children recognize the norms and values of society, the child will first absorb the norms and values that apply in his family to be part of his personality. Parents play an important role in teen emotions, both positive and negative. This shows that parents are still a very important environment for teenagers. The implications of this parent–

adolescent disagreement for mental health service use of the adolescents may be considerable (Verhulp, et al., 2015: 249).

The use of technology and the internet in a wise way will help children in various aspects throughout their lives. The exercise of internet in the blended learning model helps the children to access useful information for the lesson easily. It also helps parents to easily monitor their children by using teleconferences. In fact, blended learning is much more than a simple combination of different learning technologies (Abdalla, Soares, et al., 2012: 136 Technology that is used wisely and supervised will have a good impact on the development of children, especially to those who have single parent family and spend less time together. With the help of blended learning model, children will feel the attention and stay connected to their parents. Accordingly, an indirect character building for children is expected. This is also justified by participant 2 is parents, who states:

"Children have been given mobile phones since primary school with the pretext that, if something urgent happens, they can contact immediately. On the other hand, participant 2 is parents did not deny that they had also been called to school because their child had porn videos. They later gave extra explanation and supervision as well as punishment to cure the bad habit. In addition, to prevent the repetition of it, participant 2 is parents always check the visited or downloaded sites on their child's mobile phone."

participant 1 is parents also express the similar expectation of blended learning model:

"Actually, I was also worried to buy a gadget for my child because she does not have a full responsibility for herself at this age. Throughout the instances that I applied from the blended learning model, I feel less worried because I could control the child remotely. With this technology, my child can learn online and I get to stay connected with her, despite my busy life. I am a single parent; I have to be a mother, a father, a friend and also a backbone for the family at the same time. Thus, I have to be wise in making decisions for my child."

Blended learning model provides convenience for children in accessing lessons, especially to support their learning process in school. The internet has been widely offering helpful learning sites. The amounts of these learning sites are very advantageous for children because it gives the needed information. Blended learning model can also assist children to learn remotely; therefore they will have no difficulty in understanding the school's materials. The parents can also supervise their children because they can get connected to them continuously. Effective blended learning courses may result in greater higher-order learning and better student outcomes, benefiting students, instructors, and institutions alike (Cottle, & Glover, 2011: 207).

The role of family education in single parent families to the development of characterized children's responsible personality.

Single parent families has an impact that makes the parents sometimes unable to fully supervise the child alone because they have to take a full responsibility of their family. In addition, the parental concerns make single parents forget what they are doing, i.e. putting pressure and many restrictions, makes the children even become closed-person and cause a destruction on actions that lead them to juvenile delinquency. As informed by the parent participant 2 of research that, the more rules and pressure given to the children the more rebellious they. The participant of research provided the freedom for their children which make the parent participant 2 become a dependable companion, a friend who would lend an ear every thought of the children. On the other hand, the freedom given must also be followed with the responsibility that the child must obey. There are some restrictions that could also be applied in educating process to develop the child's personality to be more accountable. The examples for those regulations are curfewing,

smoking restriction, and asking for permission when going out or coming home late. Parents participant 2 also have some concerns about their children, but they have been trying to put their trust in their children. From the interview, the parents admitted that they are more impatient actually parents are more impatient when their children are hiding things they are doing behind them when they are too authoritarian to the child.

Thus, parents participating in this research have applied appropriate parenting style for adolescence in single parent families to form accountable character. Teenagers are children who already have a character that has been formed in peer group, society and family. The level of teenagers development requires a directive and guidance from a role model and a good environment to form their personality in order to apply the values and norms in the society, including being responsible for themselves, family, and community. Therefore, it is important for single parents to understand the application of character education in family education. Family is the earliest and main in children character formation. If the children's character is already strong then they will be able to solve every problem that comes with full responsibility. As Koesoema (2012, pp 57) discloses, character education is: "The conscious effort of man to develop the overall interrelational relational dynamics with various dimensions, both from within and from outside himself, so that the person can increasingly live his freedom so that he can be increasingly responsible for the growth of himself as a person and the development of others in their lives based on moral values that honor human dignity".

2. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the description and analysis from obtained data during the research, it can be concluded that the application of parenting and teaching for the responsible personality development in single parent family is very important for parents. Giving independence to teenagers to express their opinions within certain limits of reasonableness. With this kind of action, children can dare to set their pace, without any doubt and coercion from various parties. So they can become more responsible for what they do. Teenagers are good at choosing good friends and neighborhoods, and parents provide direction with whom and in which community teenagers should mingle. Adolescents form self-resilience to avoid being easily affected if it turns out that existing peers or communities are not in line with expectations.

The participants understand and apply character education to educate their children. On the process of teaching character education for adolescents, parents need to emphasize on deepening their understanding in order to understand the character of the child to avoid rebellion in this adolescence stage.

Based on the above conclusions, the following suggestions are given:

1. To parents always share experiences, stories and information to teenagers. So they can choose appropriate figures and attitudes to be handled in behaving.
2. To adolescents should hold the confidence that has been given by choosing parent peers good and full responsibility to keep his parent who are still living with him right now.
3. To the next researcher, the author suggests to develop the findings that have been found by the author and to then examine it with more detail and focus the research on broken home family.

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